

A FORMULA OF THE SMARANDACHE FUNCTION

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Abstract. In this paper we give a formula expressing the Smarandache function $S(n)$ by means of n without using the factorization of n .

For any positive integer n , let $S(n)$ denote the Smarandache function of n . Then we have

$$(1) \quad S(n) = \min\{a \mid a \in \mathbb{N}, n \mid a!\},$$

(See [1]). In this paper we give a formula of $S(n)$ without using the factorization of n as follows:

Theorem. For any positive integer n , we have

$$(1) \quad S(n) = n+1 - \left[\sum_{k=1}^n n^{-(n \sin(k! \pi / n))^2} \right]$$

Proof. Let $a = S(n)$. It is an obvious fact that $1 \leq a \leq n$. We see from (1) that

$$(2) \quad n \mid k!, \quad k = a, a+1, \dots, n.$$

It implies that

$$(4) \quad \frac{-(n \sin(k! \pi / n))^2}{n} = \frac{0}{n} = 1, \quad k = a, a+1, \dots, n.$$

On the other hand, since $n \nmid k!$ for $k = 1, \dots, a-1$, we have $\sin(k! \pi / n) \neq 0$ and

$$(5) \quad \left(n \sin \frac{k! \pi}{n} \right)^2 \geq \left(n \sin \frac{\pi}{n} \right)^2 > 1, \quad k = 1, \dots, a-1.$$

Hence, by (5), we get

$$(6) \quad 0 < \frac{-(n \sin(k! \pi / n))^2}{n} < 1/n, \quad k = 1, \dots, a-1.$$

Therefore, by (4) and (6), we obtain

$$(7) \quad n+1-a < \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{-(n \sin(k! \pi / n))^2}{n} < n+1-a + (a-1)/n < n+2-a.$$

Thus, by (7), we get (1) immediately. The theorem is proved.

Reference

1. F Smarandache, A function in the number theory, Smarandache function J. 1 (1990), No.1, 3 - 17.